

Enhancing Design Creativity in 11th Graders: The Role of Pinterest at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to determine (1) the use of Pinterest media among students, (2) the description of fashion design creativity among students of the Fashion Design Department, and (3) the influence of Pinterest usage on fashion design creativity in 11th grade Fashion Design students at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng. The research uses an ex post facto method. The population of the study consists of 26 students from the 11th-grade Fashion Design Department. The data collection techniques used are observation, documentation, and questionnaires. Data analysis techniques involve descriptive analysis and simple regression analysis. The results of the study show that: (1) the use of Pinterest among Fashion Design students is categorized as "excellent" category with a percentage of 91%, based on the indicator of Pinterest account usage, (2) the creativity in fashion design among the students is categorized as "excellent" with a percentage of 88.46%, based on the indicators of flexibility, originality, elaboration, and fluency, and (3) there is a significant influence of Pinterest usage (72.9%) on fashion design creativity, while 27.1% is influenced by other factors.

Keywords: Pinterest, Fashion Design, Creativity

I. INTRODUCTION

The learning process, particularly for students specializing in art and design, requires creative ideas and innovation whenever they are creating work, whether for personal, academic purposes, or to introduce it to a broader audience. Through such media, they can gather a variety of interesting inspirations and references for their work. Media such as Pinterest, Behance, Dribbble, and other online platforms are commonly used for this purpose (Rizki, 2011).

Creativity plays a crucial role for fashion design students, particularly in bridging their imaginative skills with the technical demands of the industry. For fashion design students, creativity is essential in crafting unique and innovative garments, which serve not only as artistic expression but also as practical and marketable products. Through creativity, students learn to experiment with forms, colors, materials, and styles to address both aesthetic and functional needs, setting the foundation for a successful career in the highly competitive fashion industry. Additionally, creativity enables students to push the boundaries of conventional fashion, integrating elements like sustainability and ethical design, which are becoming critical in modern fashion education (Bicho, et.al, 2024). Based on Ilham Marsudi's research (2007) the characteristics of creativity include fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration, and sensitivity.

Learning facilities refer to everything that facilitates the learning process. At vocational schools (SMKs), the available teaching and learning facilities include classrooms, libraries, cooperatives, practical rooms, electrical facilities, sewing equipment, sewing aids, and prayer rooms. The teaching and learning process in the Fashion Boutique expertise program at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng applies both theoretical and practical teaching systems. Theoretical lessons are conducted first, followed by practical activities. One of the subjects taught to 11th grade students in this expertise program is fashion-making.

An application is a computer program designed to perform specific functions for the user. The researcher chose Pinterest as the social media application in this study because (1) it was created to search for ideas or inspiration, (2) it provides unlimited fashion-related images and videos, (3) it is easy to access from gadgets

or PCs anytime and anywhere with an internet connection, and (4) it aligns with the characteristics of Generation Z, who are highly dependent on social media and technology.

Pinterest is an online media platform accessible via the internet, containing text, audio, photos, and videos. One of the platforms frequently accessed by students, especially design students, is Pinterest (Rizki, 2011). In fashion design classes, Pinterest helps students understand various models, color harmony, and trending fashion styles.

Pinterest is an alternative media tool for attracting the interest of 11th grade students in the Fashion Design Department at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng to encourage independent learning. It is hoped that Pinterest will help students visualize the process of creating fashion designs. The objectives of this study are to understand the usage of Pinterest among 11th grade students in the Fashion Design Department at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng, to assess their fashion design creativity using Pinterest, and to determine the influence of Pinterest usage on their design creativity.

II. RESEARCH DESIGN

This study employs an ex-post facto research design, which is a type of research conducted to examine events that have already occurred, subsequently looking back to identify the factors that may have caused those events (Sugiyono, 2016). This study is correlational in nature, revealing the relationship between independent and dependent variables, as follows:

Figure 1. Research Design

Note:

X = Use of Pinterest Media

Y = Creativity in Fashion Design

→ = Influence between Independent and Dependent Variable

III. DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUES

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Data collection techniques refer to the methods used to gather relevant and accurate data, whether through tests, questionnaires, observations, interviews, rating scales, or documentation. The methods utilized in this research are as follows:

A. Observation

In this study, the author has decided to employ structured observation as a data collection method. Observation is an activity conducted to understand knowledge about a phenomenon based on previously known information and ideas, in order to gather necessary information for advancing the research. The observation technique in this study is carried out through systematic and objective observation and recording of students in the Fashion Design program at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng, thereby obtaining insights into the use of Pinterest media concerning creativity in fashion design.

B. Documentation

According to Sugiyono (2018), documentation is a method used to obtain data and information in the form of books, archives, documents, writings, numbers, and images that constitute reports.

C. Questionnaire

According to Sugiyono (2018), a questionnaire is a method of data collection conducted by providing a set of written questions to respondents for their responses. This technique is an efficient means of data collection when the researcher is certain about the variables to be measured and knows what to expect from the respondents.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

Data analysis is a process used to obtain summarized data or summary numbers using specific methods or formulas. The aim of data analysis is to transform raw data from measurements into more refined data, providing direction for further examination. In this research, the data analysis techniques used to analyze and process the collected data are as follows:

A. Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive statistics are employed to analyze data by describing the collected data as it is, without intending to generalize or draw broader conclusions. In contrast, inferential statistics are techniques used to analyze sample data, with the results applicable to the population (Sugiyono, 2018).

B. Simple Analysis

Simple regression analysis is a statistical method used to test the extent of the cause-and-effect relationship between the Causal Factor Variable (X) and its Effect Variable. The Causal Factor is generally denoted by X or referred to as the Response. Simple Linear Regression (SLR) is also one of the statistical methods used in production to forecast or predict characteristics of quality and quantity. The following is the formula for simple linear regression analysis:

$$Y = \alpha + bX$$

Note:

Y = predicted value

α = constant or value when X=0

b = regression coefficient

X = value of the independent variable

C. Validation Test

The instrument validation test is a procedure for evaluating whether the questions and statements used in the questionnaire can accurately and effectively measure an object. Validity means the device can measure what it intends to measure (Sugiyono, 2018). The validation testing in this study utilized SPSS for Windows 26. To determine the validity of the questionnaire, the researcher employed a significance test by comparing the calculated r value with the table r value.

D. Hypothesis Test

To address the research question regarding the significant relationship between the use of Pinterest media and creativity in fashion design among the eleventh-grade students in the Fashion Design program at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng, a hypothesis test was conducted. The hypothesis serves as a preliminary answer to the formulated problem. Therefore, this preliminary answer must be empirically tested for its validity. The hypothesis testing in this study was conducted using simple regression techniques as follows:

H0: There is no significant relationship between Pinterest media and creativity in fashion design among the eleventh-grade students in the Fashion Design program at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng.

H1: There is a significant relationship between Pinterest media and creativity in fashion design among the eleventh-grade students in the Fashion Design program at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Pinterest media variable was measured using a single indicator, which is the Pinterest account. Descriptive statistical analysis was used to provide an overview of the data obtained from the research, aiming to avoid subjective conclusions. In this analysis, the mean method was utilized to determine and obtain the frequency values of responses from respondents and to understand the achievement levels of scores from each respondent's feedback. The achievement levels of respondents were determined based on the following criteria:

Table 1 Respondent Achievement Criteria

No	TCR Value (%)	Criteria
1	0% - 54%	Poor
2	55% - 64%	Fair
3	65% - 80%	Satisfactory
4	81% - 90%	Good
5	91% - 100%	Excellent

The questionnaire used for the Pinterest media variable consists of 7 items in the form of statements with four weighted response alternatives. To determine the distribution of respondent answers regarding these indicators, the following analysis was conducted:

Table 2 Achievement Level of Pinterest Media Variable Scores

Indicator of Creativity in Fashion Design	Number of Items	Achievement Score	Ideal Score	Respondent Achievement Level (TCR %)	Category
Pinterest Media Account	7	665	104	91.35	Excellent
Total	7	665	104	91.35	

To gain a comprehensive understanding of how Pinterest media is perceived by students in the Fashion Design program based on the previously mentioned Pinterest account indicators, the researcher accumulated these indicators through the achievement level score table, as follows:

Figure 1. Respondent Achievement Level

Based on the data in Table 2 and Fig. 1, it shows that Pinterest usage is categorized as "excellent" (91.35%). The measurement results for each item in the Pinterest media indicators demonstrate that all indicators support the quality of this variable. From the achievement score level, the highest value was obtained for the Pinterest account indicator, which implies that respondents agreed with each statement item from that indicator. The students felt that having a Pinterest account is essential for finding ideas or picture inspiration.

Each indicator used to measure Pinterest media among Fashion Design students falls within the "excellent" category. The Pinterest media account indicator is categorized as "excellent" with a percentage of 91%.

A. Creativity in Fashion Design Among 11th Grade Fashion Students at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng

To obtain a comprehensive understanding of how creativity in fashion design is perceived among students in the Fashion Design program, based on the previously mentioned variable of creativity in fashion design, the researcher accumulated the variable through the achievement level score table as follows.

Table 3 Achievement Level of Fashion Design Creativity Variable Scores

Indicator	Number of Items	Achievement Score (%)	Ideal Score	Respondent Achievement Level (TCR %)	Category
Flexibility	3	88.46%	104	88.46	Excellent
Originality	3	88.46%	105	88.46	Excellent
Elaboration	3	87.82%	106	88.46	Excellent
Fluency	2	87.50%	107	88.46	Excellent
Understanding of Design Principles and Elements	12	87.50%	108	88.46	Excellent
Total	23	4,3974	530	88.46	Excellent
Flexibility	3	88.46%	104	88.46	Excellent

Based on the data in Table 3, it can be observed that the use of Pinterest among Fashion students is in the excellent category, with a total achievement level of 88.46%, derived from the overall respondent achievement levels, which consist of 5 indicators. The measurement results for each item in the Pinterest indicators show that all indicators support the quality of this variable. The highest achievement score was obtained for the Pinterest account indicator, indicating that the respondents, namely the students, agreed with each statement item from that indicator. The students felt that having a Pinterest account is essential for finding picture inspiration. The graph can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 2. Graphic of Students' Creativity in Design

Based on Fig. 2 above, it is evident that each indicator used to assess the use of Pinterest as a medium among Fashion Design students is categorized as excellent. The flexibility indicator is categorized as excellent with a score of 88.46%, the originality indicator is also categorized as excellent with a score of 88.46%, the elaboration indicator is rated excellent with a score of 87.82%, the fluency indicator is likewise categorized as excellent with a score of 87.50%, and the fashion principle understanding and elements is rated excellent with a score of 87.50%.

B. The Influence of Pinterest on Design Creativity of 11th Grade Fashion Students

In addressing the third research question regarding the influence of Pinterest media usage on the fashion design creativity of Grade IX Fashion Design students at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng, this study applied prerequisite analysis and hypothesis testing using simple linear regression analysis. Simple linear regression analysis was employed to determine whether variations in the dependent variable could be explained by increases in the independent variable.

1. Prerequisite Analysis Testing

To ensure that the measurement tools used meet the criteria of good measurement instruments and produce accurate and appropriate data, validity and reliability tests were conducted prior to analyzing the collected data.

a. Validity Test

In this study, the validity test was used to assess whether the items in the questionnaire were valid by comparing the calculated r-value with the critical r-value as a basis for decision-making. If the calculated r-value is greater than the critical r-value, the item is considered valid. The critical r-value was determined at a significance level of 5%, with 26 respondents, yielding a critical r-value of 0.3882.

b. Normality Test Results

The normality test in regression models was used to determine whether the residual values were normally distributed. A good regression model is characterized by normally distributed residual data. If the residual data are not normally distributed, the statistical conclusions become invalid or biased. In this study, the normality test was conducted using the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov method, and the data were considered normally distributed if the significance value was greater than 0.05.

Table 4 Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		Unstandardized Residual
N		26
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	4,23519662
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,177
	Positive	,177
	Negative	-,164
Test Statistic		,177
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,035 ^c
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		

Based on the table above, it is observed that the Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) significance value is 0.035, which is greater than 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that the data are normally distributed.

2. Linearity Test

The linearity test aims to determine whether the relationship between variable X (Pinterest) and variable Y (fashion design creativity) is linear. This test is related to the use of linear regression, where the data must exhibit a linear pattern. A variable is considered to have a linear relationship if the significance of linearity is below 0.05 and the significance of the deviation from linearity is above 0.05. The researcher utilized statistical software SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) for the analysis.

Table 5 Linearity Test Results
ANOVA^a

Model		SumofSquares	df	MeanSquare	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1207,116	1	1207,116	64,606	,000 ^b
	Residual	448,422	24	18,684		
	Total	1655,538	25			

- a. Dependent Variable:Kreativitas_Mendesain_Busana
b. Predictors:(Constant),Media_Pinterest

Based on the Table 5 above, the regression model can be used to determine the constant value and test the significance of the regression coefficient hypothesis. For testing the significance of the regression coefficient at a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that Pinterest media has a significant effect on fashion design creativity.

The value of α represents the constant value, indicating that the baseline level of fashion design creativity is 2.963. The value of b represents the regression coefficient, which means that for every 1% increase in Pinterest usage, the creativity level will increase by 2.963. This equation shows that the coefficient for X is 2.963, which implies that if Pinterest usage increases by 1 point, fashion design creativity will increase by 2.963 points, with a constant value of 6.680. This equation illustrates that the higher the use of Pinterest, the higher the fashion design creativity. Therefore, it can be concluded that Pinterest usage has an influence on fashion design creativity.

3. Hypothesis Testing and Significance

Significance testing is used to determine whether the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable. The hypotheses to be tested are as follows:

H_0 : There is no significant effect of Pinterest usage on the fashion design creativity of Fashion Design students.

H_1 : There is a significant effect of Pinterest usage on the fashion design creativity of Fashion Design students.

4. Determining the Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The R^2 test is conducted to determine how much influence the independent variable, Pinterest usage, has on the dependent variable, fashion design creativity. The coefficient of determination ranges between 0 and 1, with values closer to 1 indicating a greater influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

Table 6 Results of the Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2 Test)

MODELSUMMARY^B

Model	R	RSquare	Adjusted RSquare	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,854 ^a	,729	,718	4,323

- c. Predictors:(Constant),Media_Pinterest
d. Dependent Variable:Kreativitas_Mendesain_Busana

The R-value represents the correlation coefficient, with a value of 0.854, indicating a strong relationship between Pinterest usage and fashion design creativity.

Based on the table above, it can be interpreted that 72.9% ($R^2 = 0.729$) of the variance in fashion design creativity is influenced by Pinterest usage, while the remaining 27.1% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study. Therefore, the hypothesis stating that Pinterest usage has an effect on fashion design creativity is accepted.

This research is an ex post facto study aimed at understanding the usage of Pinterest and the level of fashion design creativity among Grade XI Fashion Design students at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng, and determining the significant influence of Pinterest usage on fashion design creativity. To assess these two aspects, the

researcher distributed questionnaires via Google Forms to students who use Pinterest. Based on the analyzed data, the following discussion of the research findings is presented:

C. Overview of Pinterest Usage by Grade IX Fashion Design Students at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng

In this study, observations were made regarding the use of Pinterest, which is currently growing in popularity in Indonesia, particularly among design students. This observation was conducted by analyzing references from various Pinterest sources in the search for visual inspiration. Creativity in fashion design has been shown to be closely tied to the advancement of Pinterest as a technological platform, which allows students to easily access information and stimulate creative ideas in fashion design in line with industry advancements. This indicator was measured through seven questions on the questionnaire provided to Pinterest users. The descriptive analysis results provide the following insights into Pinterest usage among Fashion Design students:

a. Pinterest Account Ownership

Based on the data processing results table, using respondent achievement scores for the Pinterest usage variable, the study shows that the achievement score percentage is 91.35%, categorized as 'excellent.' This is attributed to the fact that most students have Pinterest accounts, making it easier for them to find visual inspiration.

Majority of the Pinterest users who served as respondents agreed with this statement. Most students not only use Pinterest to consume content but also to create or engage in creative activities by using reference images for designing fashion. The research results indicate that the primary motive for using Pinterest as a reference or source of inspiration is that Pinterest provides a wide range of relevant references tailored to users' specific needs. These references are up-to-date with current trends, and the information available on Pinterest helps users gain a better understanding of fashion, style, and the designs they require.

Users typically save pins or images that they later reference, and Pinterest fosters curiosity, especially among students, encouraging them to create. Additionally, students reported feeling more confident after seeing inspirational images on Pinterest. Among Grade XI Fashion Design students at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng, the objectives for using Pinterest vary, with one common goal being to obtain useful information that aligns with their needs.

These findings are consistent with a related study on The Influence of Using the Pinterest Application on Creativity in Designing Party Dresses among Grade XI Fashion Design 3 Students at SMK Negeri 8 Surabaya. Based on t-test analysis, the results showed $t\text{-calculated} (-4.752) > t\text{-table} (1.693)$ with a significance value Sig. (2-tailed) less than $\alpha (0.000 < 0.05)$, indicating that the research hypothesis must be accepted. From this data analysis, it can be concluded that the use of the Pinterest application has a significant impact on the creativity of designing party dresses among 11th grade Fashion Design students at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng.

D. Overview of Fashion Design Creativity among Students

Creativity in fashion design was measured using several indicators, namely flexibility, originality, elaboration, fluency, and understanding of design principles and elements. These indicators were incorporated into 23 questions in a questionnaire administered to respondents. The results of the descriptive text indicate the following insights into the creativity of fashion design students in the Fashion Design program:

1. Flexibility

Based on the scores obtained from the data processing using the achievement levels of respondents on the flexibility indicator, the results indicate an achievement percentage score of 88.46%, categorized as very good. This is reflected in the responses indicating that students generate diverse concepts in fashion design and view fashion from a broad perspective, identifying various aspects to transform into new innovations. The majority of respondents expressed agreement with this statement.

2. Originality

Regarding the originality indicator, data processing results show that students are capable of producing new and unique fashion designs that are entirely their own ideas. The study indicates an achievement percentage score of 88.46%, categorized as very good, with most respondents expressing strong agreement with this statement.

3. Elaboration

The elaboration indicator reflects that students enjoy quickly creating designs using media that are easily comprehensible, demonstrating a high level of curiosity. The research results show an achievement percentage score of 87.82%, categorized as very good, with most respondents strongly agreeing with this statement.

4. Fluency

For the fluency indicator, the results indicate that students demonstrate independence in completing complex fashion designs. The study shows an achievement percentage score of 87.50%, categorized as very good, with the majority of respondents strongly agreeing with this statement.

5. Understanding of Design Principles and Elements

The analysis of the understanding of design principles and elements shows an achievement percentage score of 87.50%, categorized as very good, with the majority of respondents strongly agreeing with this statement.

Based on the findings above, the average overall achievement level for the indicators used in this study to measure the variable of creativity in fashion design among students in the Fashion Design program is 76.8%, categorized as good.

E. Influence of Using Pinterest on Fashion Design Creativity of Students at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng

The impact of using Pinterest on students' creativity in fashion design can be substantiated through two tests: the normality test and the linearity test. According to the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test results from SPSS 26, the asymptotic significance values for both variables are as follows: variable $x = 0.200$ and variable $y = 0.200$. The significance values obtained for both variables are greater than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis is accepted or that the data from each variable is normally distributed.

Subsequently, the linearity test was conducted using the test of linearity in SPSS for Windows 26, yielding a significance value of 0.60. This indicates a linear relationship between the variable of Pinterest usage and students' creativity in fashion design, as the significance value of 0.60 is greater than 0.05. After conducting the prerequisite analysis tests, the next step involved hypothesis testing. Based on the regression coefficients table from the simple linear regression analysis, a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates a significant effect of variable (X) on variable (Y).

Moreover, the significance value of $0.006 < 0.05$ allows for the rejection of the null hypothesis, supporting the conclusion that the use of Pinterest significantly influences the creativity of fashion design students at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng. Additionally, the research obtained a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.854 between the independent and dependent variables, with an R-square value of 0.729. This R-square value indicates the extent of influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable, concluding that the use of Pinterest impacts fashion design creativity by 72.9%, while the remaining 27.1% is influenced by other factors not addressed in this study.

This finding is further corroborated by the F-calculated value of 0.469, along with a significance value of 0.000, indicating that the utilization of Pinterest collectively contributes to the influence on fashion design learning outcomes at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng. The calculation shows a contribution of 35.032%, while 66.968% of fashion design learning outcomes are affected by factors outside the scope of this study.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis and discussion conducted previously, the depiction of Pinterest among students of the Fashion Education Program in grade 11th at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng is categorized as very good, as

the majority of respondents who use media Pinterest expressed strong agreement with the statement formulated in one indicator of media Pinterest, namely having a Pinterest account. The portrayal of creativity in fashion design among students of the Fashion Education Program in Class XI at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng is also categorized as very good, as most respondents in this study expressed strong agreement with the statements formulated across five indicators of fashion design creativity: flexibility, originality, elaboration, fluency, and understanding of the principles and elements of design. The results of the hypothesis test reveal a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating that there is an effect of variable (X) on variable (Y). Furthermore, the calculated t-value is 8.038, with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$, leading to the conclusion that the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. This indicates that media Pinterest has a significant effect on the creativity of fashion design among students of the Fashion Education Program in Class XI at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng. The correlation coefficient (R) between the independent and dependent variables is 0.854, with an R-squared value of 0.729. The R-squared value demonstrates the extent of influence that the independent variable has on the dependent variable. Consequently, it can be concluded that the influence of media Pinterest on the creativity of fashion design students is 72.9%, while 27.1% is affected by other factors.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, which demonstrate the influence of media Pinterest on the creativity of fashion design students in the Fashion Education Program Class XI at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng, the researcher provides the following recommendations: The use of media Pinterest significantly facilitates students in seeking visual inspiration, particularly when they lack ideas or references. The inspirational images found often align with the principles and elements of fashion design. Therefore, most students utilize media Pinterest for their fashion design coursework. Enhancement of Fashion Design Creativity. While creativity in fashion design among students of the Fashion Education Program in Class XI at SMK Negeri 1 Bantaeng is evident, there is still a noted deficiency in modifying or accurately rendering designs. Media Pinterest allows students to enhance their creativity and innovation in producing unique designs. The influence of media Pinterest on the creativity of fashion design students is indicative of the general evolution of educational media in Indonesia, as well as the growth of media Pinterest, which greatly aids students in design creation. Many students still struggle to design in accordance with the principles and elements of fashion design. Therefore, it is essential for both the community and students to understand better how to produce fashion design works, and to wisely seek out appropriate and user-friendly educational media for learning purposes

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